

URBANIZATION OF MICRO-REGIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article explores the concept and processes of micro-regional urbanization in the Republic of Uzbekistan. While the national average level of urbanization is close to the global average, there is significant variation at the district level. The study introduces the term “*micro-regional urbanization*” to describe localized urban transformation in rural districts, where urban infrastructure, economic activity, and socio-cultural change are beginning to emerge. Based on data from 163 districts, the study proposes a classification by urbanization level and economic specialization, offering recommendations for targeted regional development.

Keywords. Micro-regional urbanization; rural transformation; urbanization levels; district classification; spatial development; urban-rural integration; Uzbekistan; territorial restructuring; regional specialization.

Introduction. Although the average urbanization level of the Republic of Uzbekistan is close to the global average, there is a significant disparity among its administrative units. In this context, the present article analyzes urbanization indicators at the district, or “micro-region,” level by examining the traditionally used methods for determining average urbanization levels across regions. In this study, the term “urbanization of micro-regions” refers to local transformation processes occurring in rural districts – namely, the gradual penetration of urban functions into lower-level territories and the resulting changes in the population’s lifestyle. Urbanization processes in rural districts remain an under-researched area. In such areas, urbanization is manifested through the activation of local centers – markets, bus terminals, neighborhood buildings, and infrastructure networks (natural gas, high-speed internet), the emergence of recreational zones and wellness facilities, and the widespread adoption of urban lifestyles. This includes the development of entrepreneurial activity among residents and the planned construction of private homes and neighborhood streets. Based on the above analyses, the urbanization of micro-regions can be defined as follows: Micro-regional urbanization refers to a localized, small-scale form of urbanization occurring in rural districts or peri-urban areas. It is characterized by emerging urban traits such as increased economic activity, infrastructural development, shifts in socio-cultural life, and urban-style land use patterns.

It is important to note that in this study, the term “*micro-regional urbanization*” is being introduced into scientific discourse for the first time by the author. Here, “micro-regions” refer to local areas situated at the lower levels of urbanization, which are administratively part of rural districts but are functionally and infrastructurally demonstrating signs of urban transformation. Through this concept, the study explores how urban infrastructure, socio-cultural changes, and economic activity are evolving at the micro level. This approach is functionally similar to international concepts such as “*local urbanization*” and “*peripheral urban transition*,” but is proposed here as an independent scientific concept specific to the context of Uzbekistan. The concept of micro-regional urbanization encompasses the spatial variation of urbanization, the merging of rural and urban functions, and the transformation of lifestyles. It draws on foundational theories such as F.Ratzel’s and J.H.fon Thünen’s center-periphery and land use models, D.Harvey’s and E.Soja’s theories of territorial and socio-spatial transformation, and the models of “*global city*” , “*innovation hub*,” and “*urban functional diffusion*” developed by S.Sassen and R.Florida. Accordingly, micro-regional urbanization can be understood not only as a geographical phenomenon but also as a process of territorial, economic, cultural, and political restructuring.

For example, in districts formerly characterized by a purely agrarian function and located at a significant distance (30–40 km) from regional centers or large cities, the emergence of major markets, bus terminals, bank branches, shopping centers, private clinics, youth innovation hubs, small enterprises, and entrepreneurial facilities represent tangible manifestations of micro-regional urbanization [2]. Studying urbanization processes at the lower level – specifically within rural districts – enables a deeper analysis of spatial disparities in urbanization trends. It also allows for the identification of districts where urbanization needs to be activated and helps assess the available opportunities to increase the urbanization level for each micro-region. Ultimately, this provides a foundation for developing clear and actionable plans for promoting urbanization at the micro-regional level. In this research, the urbanization levels of 163 rural districts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of 2025, were examined. Based on the results, rural districts were grouped into nine categories by urbanization percentage: below 10%, 10–20%, 20–30%, 30–40%, 40–50%, 50–60%, 60–70%, 70–80%, and above 80%.

To improve the precision and reliability of micro-level urbanization data, available indicators were analyzed for both 2010 (when major urban policy

reforms were initiated) and 2025. It was found that the overall national urbanization rate declined by 0.7% during this period, which also led to negative changes at the district level. For instance, in January 2010, two districts had urbanization rates above 80% – Taxiatosh (100.0%) and Markhamat (81.0%). However, by January 2025, only one district – Uchquduq (87.5%) – remained in this category. Moreover, the number of districts with urbanization rates below 10% increased from three (Samarkand – 5.1%, Kogon – 6.6%, Mirzaobod – 8.7%) to four (Samarkand – 6.2%, Kogon – 7.6%, Mirzaobod – 9.3%, Qo’shrabot – 9.3%). In 2010, a total of 32 districts had urbanization levels above the national average (51.7%), while in 2025, only 29 districts exceeded the national average urbanization level (51.0%). This demonstrates a general decline in urbanization not only at the national but also at the district scale. As of 2025, more than four-fifths of all districts (134 out of 163) have urbanization rates below 50% – i.e., below the national average.

We argue that accelerating urbanization processes in these districts should be considered a priority within Uzbekistan’s urban development strategy. A detailed analysis of micro-regional urbanization reveals that in 68 districts, the urbanization rate is below 30% [2]. Based on urbanization levels and economic specialization, all districts of the Republic were categorized into four conditional groups: agrarian, agrarian-industrial, industrial-agrarian, and industrial (see Table). It must be noted that this classification is indicative and that some districts may not fully align with the given typology. This is primarily due to the natural geographic conditions and the availability of natural resources, which determine the regional division of labor.

Table

Clustering the micro-regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the level of urbanization and economic specialization

No	Territorial Units	Agrarian type – urbanization level below 30%	Agro-industrial type – urbanization level between 30% and 50%	Industrial-agrarian type – urbanization level between 50% and 75%	Industrial or service sector (Post-Industrial) type – above 75%
	Republic of Uzbekistan	68	66	23	6
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	6	6	3	1
	Regions (viloyat)				

2	Andijan	1	10	1	2
3	Bukhara	8	2	1	-
4	Jizzakh	3	7	2	-
5	Namangan	-	5	6	-
6	Navoi	2	4	1	1
7	Kashkadarya	6	5	2	1
8	Samarkand	12	2	-	-
9	Syrdarya	4	3	1	-
10	Surkhandarya	6	8	-	-
11	Tashkent	8	6	1	-
12	Fergana	4	5	5	1
13	Khorezm	8	3	-	-

The table was compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Typically, regions with unfavorable natural conditions for agriculture and limited access to water and land resources tend to have higher levels of urbanization. In contrast, traditionally agricultural areas and newly developed territories – especially districts located near major agglomerations – often display lower levels of urbanization. However, in the districts of the Fergana Valley, a high population density within settlements originally founded on traditional agricultural systems has led to a shortage of fertile land. This, in turn, forces the population to shift their economic activities toward non-agricultural sectors. As a result, district-level specialization begins to change, contributing to the gradual increase in urbanization levels.

In the core study area of Southern Uzbekistan, districts such as Ko'kdala (15.6%), Bandixon (18.0%), Dehqonobod (19.1%), Sariosiyo (19.2%), Jarqo'rg'on (20.1%), Uzun (23.3%), G'uzor (23.5%), Qamashi (23.8%), Shahrisabz (24.1%), Qiziriq (26.6%), Chiroqchi (28.8%), and Sherobod (29.9%) are characterized by agrarian specialization. Interestingly, G'uzor and Jarqo'rg'on are among the leading industrial-producing districts in their respective provinces. The inclusion of Shahrisabz District in this group can be explained by the administrative separation of Shahrisabz city in 2018, which had served as the district center but was reclassified as a city under provincial subordination. Notably, in 2010, the urbanization level of the district was 53.2%. In Qashqadaryo Region, five districts are categorized as having agrarian-industrial specialization – Yakkabog' (32.6%), Qarshi (36.2%), Kitob (37.3%), Mirishkor (37.7%), and Kasbi (38.6%) – yet all fall below the regional average urbanization rate of 42.7%. The industrial base of these districts is primarily concentrated in light industry and food production. In Surkhandaryo Region,

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there are eight such districts, four of which – Muzrabot, Oltinsoy, Boysun, and Angor – exceed the regional average urbanization rate of 36.1%.

Only three districts in Southern Uzbekistan have urbanization levels above the national average, and all are located in Qashqadaryo Region. These include Koson (52.6%), the region's most populous district; Nishon (60.0%), labeled an "innovation district" which produced one-quarter of the region's industrial output in 2024; and Muborak (79.5%), a district with arid desert conditions that is specialized in natural gas processing. Notably, in these districts, the level of urbanization aligns with their economic specialization, and they also lead in terms of the proportion of the population employed in non-agricultural sectors [1].

Conclusion. In general, fostering urbanization processes in Uzbekistan requires attention not only to major cities under national and regional jurisdiction but also to micro-regions with urbanization rates below the national average. It is essential to identify potential urban centers within these districts that could serve as future poles of economic growth and to develop targeted development programs accordingly.

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